

TO INTRODUCE A STATE OF EMERGENCY LEGAL BASIS

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Abstract: this article covers the concept of a state of emergency, when and in what case a state of emergency is declared, the types of state of emergency, the grounds for the introduction of a state of emergency, the obligations of citizens in an emergency, the types of liability for violation of the state of emergency.

Key words: referendum, Constitution, state of emergency, constitutional order, weapons, ammunition, explosives, special means, toxic substances, curfew.

It is known that these days an important political process in our country continues to conduct a nationwide discussion on amendments and additions to the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Of course, the constitutional reforms of our motherland today and it is a matter of extraordinary importance for the future life. Our multinational people offer many of its own in discussions and comments. Total from citizens to date 48,492 offers were received.

Comprehensive work is being carried out to build a new Uzbekistan. Over the past 6 years, our entire society has reawakened people are striving to think, work and live in a new way. It was in these democratic renewal processes that the commission for the improvement of constancy was established, as the need arose to update and improve our general constitution in accordance with the requirements of today's life.

So far, a total of 48,492 proposals have been received from citizens to amend the Constitution. It should be noted separately that the draft constitutional law "on amendments and additions to the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan" is subject to a general discussion. After that, it is brought to perfection by the legislative chamber on the basis of the opinions and comments expressed by citizens. Then this project will be put into the referendum of the Republic of Uzbekistan and our citizens will express their will on this issue by voting freely. Only then will the amendments and additions introduced into the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan be of legal nature."

But in some places there are cases of misunderstanding in the interpretation of the essence of this issue. In particular, some norms concerning the Republic of Karakalpakstan, which are envisaged in the project, were

protested by a group of persons. As a result of this, on July 1 of this year, demonstrations were organized on the central streets of the city of Nukus.

A group of persons, on July 1, 2022, in Nukus city, disguised fake slogans on himself, to the confidence of citizens entering, distracting their opinion, without submitting to the legal requirements of representatives of the authorities, he caused riots, tried to seize the premises of local government bodies.

They continued to commit acts of vandalism on July 2, 2022 on the main streets in the administrative center of the Republic, without listening to the demands to stop actions aimed at violating public order.

In addition, some of the people who participated in the riots tried to provoke clashes with law enforcement officers, violently invade protected areas, throwing stones and various objects at the buildings.

During the walk through the city, they caused significant damage to infrastructure facilities. They broke the windows of buildings and made fires. Several groups attempted to take over the buildings of the Nukus City Main Department of internal affairs and the National Guard Department in order to capture the weapons.

These people took advantage of the relative advantage in terms of number, attacking law enforcement officers, beating them shamelessly and inflicting severe bodily injuries.

In this regard, by the decree of the head of State on July 02, 2022 of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan Paragraph 19 of Article 93 and "Emergency" of the Republic of Uzbekistan to articles 5-7 of the constitutional law "on status" in accordance with the order of the president of the Republic of Karakalpakstan on July 3, 2022 from 00:01 to 00: 00 on August 2, 2022 during the period, a curfew was introduced from 21:00 to 07:00 during the period of the state of emergency and state of emergency.

So when and in what situation is a state of emergency declared?

In the constitutional law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "on state of emergency", the concept of state of emergency is as follows the tariff is granted, that is, the right of citizens of the Republic of Uzbekistan, foreign citizens and stateless persons state administration bodies, local government bodies, self-government bodies of citizens, NGOs and other organizations, regardless of the organizational and legal and ownership form, which allow to establish certain restrictions provided for by this constitutional law in relation to the freedoms and rights of legal entities, as well as the rights of legal entities, and impose

additional obligations on them, which are, a separate legal regime of the activities of their officials.

Curfew - daily without special issued permits and there is a ban on staying outside the streets and other public places or accommodation without identity documents time. Goals for the introduction of an emergency state its introduction it consists in eliminating the circumstances that served as the basis for ensuring the safety of citizens of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the protection of the constitutional system and territorial integrity of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

The state of emergency is introduced in exceptional cases in the presence of situations that directly threaten the Life, Health and safety of citizens of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the constitutional system and (or) territorial integrity of the Republic of Uzbekistan, and cannot be eliminated without the use of emergency measures. The sentence for such cases includes:

Real external danger, attempts to forcibly change the constitutional system and (or) territorial integrity of the Republic of Uzbekistan, mass riots, terrorist acts, as well as acts of violence, which occur simultaneously with acts of violence, directly threatening the Life, Health and safety of citizens, the daily activities of state bodies, other organizations blocking extremely important and categorized objects or certain places or occupation, preparation (organization) of illegal armed structures and their activities, interethnic, inter-confessional and border disputes;

large accidents, natural disasters, epidemics, as well as other natural and man-made emergencies, Emergency environmental situations that require the implementation of comprehensive emergency rescue work and other non-delayed work.

The state of emergency is introduced by the decree of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan on the entire territory or in some places of the Republic of Uzbekistan and is immediately published in the media.

According to Article 13 of the law, real external danger, attempts to forcibly change the constitutional system and (or) territorial integrity of the Republic of Uzbekistan, mass riots, terrorist acts, as well as acts of violence that occur at the same time, directly threatening the Life, Health and safety of citizens, the daily activities of state bodies, other organizations, blocking or occupation of extremely important and, in the event of inter-confessional and border disputes, the following emergency measures and temporary restrictions may apply:

introduction of curfew;

implementation of territorial defense measures;

restriction of such activities with the indication of the conditions and procedure for limiting the activities of the media, as well as the temporary seizure or correspondence of a printed product, radio-emitting, sound amplifying media, copy reproduction techniques, the establishment of a separate procedure for conducting journalists' accreditation;

suspension of activities of non-profit organizations that are hindering the elimination of cases that served as the basis for the introduction of a state of emergency;

Conducting personal examination of citizens of the Republic of Uzbekistan, foreign citizens, stateless persons, examination of documents confirming their identity, inspection of items, housing and vehicles;

the Prohibition of the realization of weapons, its ammunition, explosives, special means, toxic substances, the establishment of a special mode of circulation of drugs and preparations, ethyl alcohol, alcohol products, which contain narcotic drugs and their analogues, psychotropic and potent substances. In exceptional cases, the temporary seizure of weapons and ammunition from citizens, weapons and its ammunition from organizations, special means and toxic substances, as well as combat and training-combat military equipment, explosives and radioactive substances;

expulsion of persons who violate the state of emergency and do not live in the territory in which the state of emergency was introduced in the prescribed manner at their own expense outside the territory, and in the absence of funds in them, the replacement of expenses at the expense of the state budget of the Republic of Uzbekistan with subsequent collection

To ensure the state of emergency, the forces and means of the Ministry of internal affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the National Guard, the State Security Service and the Ministry of emergency situations, as well as other state bodies and organizations of the Republic of Uzbekistan that are part of the State System of emergency prevention and action are used.

In relation to persons who violate the rules of the curfew introduced along with the state of emergency, the Republic of Uzbekistan is subject to liability in accordance with the code of administrative responsibility.

According to Article 28 of the law, persons who violate the rules of the curfew are held until the end of the curfew, while persons who do not have identity documents (hiding information about their identity) with them can be

held for a maximum period of twenty-four hours according to the decision of the head of the internal affairs body.

Persons held, things that are next to them and documents, as well as their vehicles, can be examined in the manner prescribed by law.

